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The Communicative Function of Writing in the Relationship Between Graphic Design and Public Space

Grafik Tasarım ve Kamusal Alan İlişkisinde İletişim Aracı Olarak Yazı

ABSTRACT

Public space can be defined as a space for communication where social interaction takes place, open to every individual living in society. While public space is associated with public life, it is also described as a space for expression, gathering, and organization. As a space where common interests are at stake, public space can be defined as a space shared by every individual in society. Graphic design plays a significant role in the visual organization of this space, and typography serves as one of the fundamental elements of graphic design in facilitating communication within the public space. In the public space, typography fulfills roles such as providing information, wayfinding, and visual identification through typography, wayfinding systems, environmental graphic design applications, and urban graphics. In this study, based on qualitative research methods, previous academic studies and scientific sources on the subject were systematically reviewed and evaluated as part of a literature review. First, the concept of public space was explained from the perspectives of various thinkers and examined with examples. Furthermore, the study focuses on the function of text in the relationship between graphic design and public space, and within this framework, it presents examples of text and typography in public spaces located in various settings. The study concludes that text in public spaces not only serves the purpose of ensuring the legibility and communication of the space but also plays a role in social communication and cultural identity.

Keywords: Graphic Design, type, typography, communication, public space

ÖZET

Kamusal alan, toplumda yaşayan her bireyin kullanımına açılmış olan toplumsal etkileşimin kurulduğu bir iletişim mekânı olarak açıklanabilmektedir. Kamusal alan, kamusal yaşamla ilişkili olmakla birlikte, bir ifade, bir bir araya gelme ve örgütlenme alanı olarak da ifade edilmektedir. Ortak çıkarların söz konusu olduğu kamusal mekân, toplumda yer alan her birey için ortak olan alan olarak tanımlanabilmektedir. Bu mekânın görsel olarak organizasyonunun sağlanmasında grafik tasarım önemli bir görev üstlenmekte ve yazı da kamusal mekânda iletişimin sağlanmasında grafik tasarımın temel unsurlarından biri olarak yer almaktadır. Yazı, kamusal alanda tipografi, yönlendirme sistemleri, çevresel grafik tasarım uygulamaları, kent grafikleri aracılığıyla bilgilendirme, yönlendirme, görsel kimliklendirme gibi rolleri üstlenmektedir. Çalışmada, nitel araştırma yöntemine dayanarak literatür tarama kapsamında konu hakkında daha önce yapılan akademik çalışmalar ve bilimsel kaynaklar sistemli bir şekilde incelenerek, değerlendirilmiş ve öncelikle kamusal alan kavramı farklı düşünürlerin perspektifinden açıklanmış ve örneklerle ele alınmıştır. Bununla birlikte devamında grafik tasarım ve kamusal alan ilişkisinde yazının işlevine odaklanılmış ve bu çerçevede farklı mekânlarda yer alan kamusal alanda yazı ve tipografi örneklerine yer verilmiştir. Çalışma sonucunda yazının kamusal alanda, alanın okunurluğu ve iletişiminin sağlanması görevinin yanı sıra aynı zamanda toplumsal iletişim, kültürel kimlik ve bellek aktarımında rol oynayan bir unsur olduğu sonucuna varılmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Grafik Tasarım, yazı, tipografi, iletişim, kamusal alan.

1. INTRODUCTION

The public space is not only a physical place but also a cultural and social arena where visual communication practices are produced and displayed, and where experiences are shaped based on the principle of social benefit. Viewed from this perspective, graphic design also produces work that enhances the legibility and accessibility of public spaces, guided by the principle of social benefit. In particular, informational and wayfinding designs created through typography, as well as digital screens used in indoor and outdoor spaces, play a significant role in shaping individuals' relationship with the public sphere. In his book *The Structural Transformation of the Public Sphere*, sociologist Jürgen Habermas (1993:2) defines the public sphere as a center of interaction for communication and traces its origins to various historical periods. The visual systems used in public spaces defined as centers of communication contribute to the realization of this communication. As a result, graphic design exists not only as a discipline that produces aesthetic works through its expressive tools but also as a social tool that regulates individuals' presence and daily lives within the public sphere.

Wayfinding design, informational graphics, and signage created using typographic systems in cities also shape the way people perceive their surroundings. Functionally designed modern typographic approaches have led to the establishment of standardized visual communication models in public spaces. Subway maps, wayfinding systems, and typography used on architectural surfaces in cities are among the most important examples of graphic design in public spaces. These systems transform the complex and crowded nature of urban life into a legible, systematic, and simple visual language.

2. THE CONCEPT OF PUBLIC SPACE

The public sphere refers to the physical or conceptual spaces where individuals living in a society come together to discuss common issues, thereby fostering social interaction and communication. The public sphere can also be defined as spaces open for the collective use of society, where individuals engage with one another on social, political, cultural, and everyday matters. Jürgen Habermas (2004:95), on the other hand, describes the public sphere primarily as a space within social life that is accessible to all individuals. Hannah Arendt (2006:92) defines the concept of the public sphere from two distinct perspectives: public exposure and the shared world. Public spaces are areas accessible to all individuals that contribute to the formation of a shared social life. The organization of public spaces is crucial for meeting the needs of individuals living in society (Çelik, Bingöl, & Özkul, 2019, p. 286). The diversity of public spaces in cities reveals the city's social and cultural connections. The relationship between these spaces and cultural and social activities also provides insight into the power of public spaces in social life.

The concept of public space has become a field of research for various disciplines, including the social sciences, political science, communication studies, architecture, and design. Public space is not only a physical space available for use by every member of society but also a space for communication where individuals can engage in various discussions and where ideas are formed. Habermas (1962:369) describes the public sphere as an arena for perceiving, diagnosing, and resolving problems that affect the entire society. In line with this approach, the public sphere can be defined as a space that is accessible to every member of society and plays a role in the production of social interaction.

Art and design practices in public spaces play a pioneering role in shaping social communication. Artistic activities created in public spaces have enabled art to move beyond enclosed spaces such as museums and galleries, integrating with society and engaging in interaction with it. From this perspective, public spaces can be characterized not only as venues where art is exhibited but also as cultural platforms that foster social communication and shared experiences. According to Sibel Yardımcı (2014:133), exhibition spaces are not only significant as public spaces but are also important in terms of their contribution to the process of socialization. Regardless of whether they are enclosed or open, public spaces not only foster communication among individuals in society but also enable the creation of a shared experiential environment. The public space created through the temporary architectural structures within the Serpentine Pavilion—organized by the Serpentine Gallery in Kensington Gardens, London is an open-air project that brings together concepts such as contemporary art and architectural experimentation. Since 2000, this annual summer event has transformed the park into an interactive social space featuring a temporary public space designed by architects who have not previously undertaken architectural projects in the UK. In the 2025 phase of this project, the concepts of permanence and transience were brought into public discourse through a nomadic library concept (Figure 1) a space created around a tree using wooden and kinetic capsules designed by a Bangladeshi architect.

Figure 1: Serpentine Pavillion, Marina Tabassum,2025. **Source:** URL 1

Artworks in public spaces raise awareness of issues among individuals and engage them intellectually in the process. The monument titled “Women of World War II,” located in Whitehall, London (Figure 2), uses both visual elements and text to illustrate how women on the home front took on critical roles by donning uniforms in place of their husbands while the men were fighting at the front, and how they subsequently returned to their daily lives by taking off and hanging up their uniforms when their husbands returned from the front. This monument, situated in the city center, serves as a reminder and raises awareness in the public consciousness of the efforts and sacrifices women made during the war.

Figure 2: Monument to Woman of World II, John W. Mills, 2005. **Source:** Photographed by Author.

2.1. Public Space, Visual Communication and Writing

Public space refers to a social and cultural arena where individuals can communicate, exchange information, and create shared experiences. The discipline of visual communication is a key tool that not only implements arrangements and designs to facilitate the flow of information within the public space but also guides the spatial experience and makes interactions visible. Wayfinding and informational designs, typography, pictograms, symbols, signs, and digital displays are all examples of visual communication practices found in public spaces.

Throughout history, texts and textual arrangements created by different nations and civilizations have been used in various public spaces and made available to the public. Emre Becer (2019:176) defines typography—described as a design-oriented form of writing—as a key element of communication with the broadest and most essential scope of application, emphasizing its legibility. Uçar (2016:95), on the other hand, approaches typography as a visual element that records the passage of time in visual communication. Looking at the historical process from this perspective, while the Egyptians used the hieroglyphic writing system in a stylized manner on monumental stone temples and tombs, the Greeks incorporated details of the Ionic alphabet into their temples. The Rosetta Stone (Figure 3), dating from the Ancient Egyptian period in 196 BC and inscribed in three different writing systems, is also among the examples of the function of writing to inform the public in public spaces (Meggs & Purvis, 2012, p. 14). During the Roman period, the

Romans utilized writing in public spaces by employing Roman inscriptions on buildings in towns and in public areas. The Taj Mahal, construction of which began in the 1630s, was built as a public structure featuring Islamic inscriptions in calligraphic form (Poulin, 2012, pp. 28–34). In Turkish states, both during the pre-Islamic and post-Islamic periods, writing was used as an important tool in public spaces and architecture. In his book ‘Turkish Art’ (2018:386), Oktay Aslanapa describes writing as an important tool used in architecture on various surfaces such as stone, brick, ceramic, wood, metal, and textiles and, in particular, as a vital element that brings architecture to life.

Figure 3: Rosetta Stone, 196 BC. **Source:** URL 2.

In addition, writing was used as a means of communication on monuments erected in public spaces—such as Turkish inscriptions—to convey the state’s sovereignty, power, and messages intended for the people. It is evident that public communication was achieved through the language used in these inscriptions and the expressions that highlighted national consciousness and state power.

Following the Industrial Revolution, the emergence of new urban centers, changes in modes of transportation, and the expansion of public spaces in city squares led to an increase in the use of writing, making it essential for communication in public spaces in daily life. Changes in the construction sector during and after the 20th century, along with developments in the tourism industry, have also contributed to the emergence of writing as a communication tool that defines the space in public areas. In particular, at airports, hospitals, museums, places of worship, and city squares, it serves as an element that identifies the space, provides information about it, and guides users.

Through visual communication, wayfinding systems, city and subway maps, traffic signs, and touch-screen digital displays, they fulfill their most basic function in public spaces. Kevin Lynch (2014:5), author of the book ‘The Image of the City’, focuses on how a good environmental image in cities instills a sense of security in the individuals living there and emphasizes that this also reflects on the relationships people establish with the outside world. Celal Abdi Güzer (2024:15) also describes this phenomenon as objects physically present in the environment serving as key elements that represent the city’s identity, history, traditions, priorities, challenges, and well-being. From this perspective, visual objects found in cities and public spaces also instill a sense of security in individuals and contribute to the details of the city’s identity. According to Uçar (2016:21), in settings such as international airports and international sporting events where people from different linguistic and cultural backgrounds gather visual communication tools are preferred to facilitate communication.

Figure 4: Berlin subway type examples. **Source:** Photographed by author

Graphic design tools, which play an active role in facilitating visual communication, are effective in shaping identity in public spaces through the typefaces and color systems they employ. Becer (2019:184) views typography which he defines as a key element of graphic communication as a dynamic structure in communication. Text and the letters that compose it become part of the physical environment and specific central locations, functioning as systems that integrate with these locations (Jean, 2023, p. 130). As a result, this contributes to the formation of concepts such as a sense of belonging to the public sphere, the formation of cultural memory and representation, and the sense of unity in the appearance of a space. Elif Atamaz (2022:254) emphasizes that visual communication design plays a significant role by providing information about the existing space, guiding users, and imparting an identity to the space, while also highlighting the use of graphic design tools.

Figure 5: 'Follow Your Dreams', Banksy, 2010.
Source: URL 3

Figure 6: 'Create Escape', Banksy, 2021.
Source: URL 4

At some subway stations in Berlin located along the former East-West divide, station names and directional signs—created using Gothic typefaces that evoke the past and the historical process that has unfolded—are still in use. With the fall of the Berlin Wall, modern-style typefaces were also used in newly constructed subway stations (Figure 4), creating an urban atmosphere in the city's public spaces where the old and the new coexist.

Tools that facilitate visual communication in public spaces such as signage systems, street signs, and graffiti on walls not only convey information but also contribute to the formation of a city's cultural memory and identity. Graffiti artist Banksy establishes a relationship between visual imagery and text in his works to convey meaningful messages to his target audience in public spaces. With his 2010 work in Boston (Figure 5), he sought to deliver an ironic message in the public sphere through the interplay of text and figurative composition. In 2021, with his massive stencil graffiti piece (Figure 6) on the wall of Reading Prison in England, he referenced the prison days of the famous author Charles Dickens, depicting the prisoner's escape by tying up the papers emerging from his typewriter thus presenting this narrative as graffiti and highlighting the function of creating a social memory in the public sphere. As a result, this fosters a sense of belonging to the city among individuals. According to Roland Barthes (2022:45), these

visual tools in the city carry not only their direct meaning but also connotations related to culture and ideology. The typographic systems and design language used in maps, mobile apps, and information panels within urban transportation systems also reveal the concept of public order established through visual communication.

Writing is one of the fundamental tools for facilitating communication and establishing order in public spaces. In cities, writing also enables the formation of concepts such as cultural memory and identity that individuals associate with the city. From a graphic design perspective, the use of writing in urban spaces is viewed as a visual system that guides individuals' experiences and provides aesthetic coherence.

2.1.1. The Spatial and Visual Function of Writing in the Public Sphere

As the most fundamental tool of communication, typography not only conveys information but also serves as an element that guides users through a space and facilitates flow and organization within it. Signs in city squares, digital screens, and graphic design applications created to reflect the environment all contribute to the relationship an individual establishes with the space. From this perspective, text used in public spaces constitutes a communication system that highlights the functional and aesthetic characteristics inherent in the graphic design perspective.

Figure 7: London Charles Dickens Museum Street Wayfinding Sign Board. **Source:** Photographed by author

Figure 8: 'Kill Your Speed, Not A Child' sign board. **Source:** Photographed by author

Figure 7 shows that the direction of the Charles Dickens Museum building in the city center is indicated by signs featuring text. As Emre Becer (2019:33) notes, graphic design is a visual communication art whose primary function is to convey a message. Based on this, graphic design fundamentally fulfills its role of conveying messages by utilizing the inherent characteristics of typographic systems. Figure 8 shows how effective messages regarding speed and vehicle usage within the city are conveyed to drivers in London via a yellow warning sign featuring meaningful text.

Applications of typography and graphic design in urban wayfinding networks, rail systems, and airports not only ensure that these spaces are represented in a more systematic and clear language but also facilitate individuals' spatial experiences. Richard Poulin (2012:11) emphasizes that typographic forms and graphic styles including classical inscriptions, figurative murals, and ornamented surfaces work in collaboration with architecture to influence the understanding of cities' visual representations. He further states that graphic design, by integrating with all these elements, contributes to shaping the lives of city dwellers. From this perspective, the typefaces and typographic arrangements used in public spaces contribute visually to the aesthetics of cities through their letterforms, colors, and proportions. Artistic examples encountered in cultural centers and exhibition spaces demonstrate how typography contributes to the atmosphere of a given space.

2.1.1.2. The Role of Writing as A Guide in Public Space

In modern cities, where transportation networks are complex and large-scale public buildings and spaces are constructed areas characterized by dense crowds text serves as a wayfinding element and an essential component of spatial communication. From this perspective, text and typography not only convey information in environmental graphic design applications and signage systems but also shape how individuals perceive their surroundings. Street signs, directional signs within transportation systems, and information panels help individuals orient themselves within the spatial structure. In this regard, Adrian Frutiger (1998:117) emphasizes that typefaces used in public spaces must be legible and easily perceivable, allowing users to read them effortlessly.

Figure 9: London Kings Cross Station Underground Wayfinding sign board.

Source: Photographed by author

From a graphic design perspective, the text in wayfinding systems should present information within a hierarchical structure and ensure that users reach the correct destination. These arrangements, created under the umbrella of environmental graphic design, involve the systematic and planned organization of various forms, typography, and colors in urban spaces such as public areas (Esgehzadeh Torbai, 2018, p. 1951). The directional signs used in the wayfinding system at King's Cross train station in the United Kingdom which serves as both a national and international transportation hub (Figure 9) are among the examples that demonstrate the functional use of text in public spaces. Features such as visual hierarchy and color are effectively utilized in the text to enhance the legibility of the space for users and to assist with wayfinding within the space's flow. In this space, text serves as the primary communication element through visual imagery created using primary colors.

2.1.1.3 The Role of Writing in the Formation of Identity in the Public Sphere

In addition to its role in conveying information in public spaces, typography serves as a tool that contributes to the visual expression of urban identity, fosters a sense of spatial belonging among individuals, and helps shape the collective memory of the city. Details related to graphic design and typography in urban spaces enhance individuals' visual literacy and help them develop a sense of belonging to the city commensurate with their own identity (Esgehzadeh Torbai, 2018, p. 1951). From this perspective, typography is a visual tool that carries and conveys urban culture in public spaces within cities. According to Ellen Lupton, typography used in public spaces conveys cultural meaning through its scale and form (Lupton, 2010, p. 8). The typefaces used in city squares can help create an atmosphere that perpetuates the city's historical process and social memory. Recently, in many city centers and public spaces, the typefaces used have come to represent historical memory as a presentation of the city's identity.

Figure 10: İstanbul Grand Bazaar Beyazid Door.
Source: Photographed by author

Figure 11: Borough Market Door.
Source: Photographed by author

The Grand Bazaar (Figure 10), one of Istanbul's oldest commercial centers, conveys the impression to visitors that it is a site of significant cultural heritage through the use of text in the inscription areas and on the plaques at its various entrances; at the same time, it ensures the structure stands out in the square where it is located, thereby establishing its identity. Furthermore, it facilitates a connection to Istanbul's historical and cultural identity. Similarly, Borough Market (Figure 11), one of London's oldest food markets, references its historical evolution through the use of text within the space and emphasizes the city's historical identity. Both the text displayed at the market's entrance and the text installations inside the market help shape the historical identity the space has established through its history and culinary culture. With digitalization, the use of typography for identity-building in public spaces is also taking shape in urban environments through applications created by digital systems. The brands, slogans, and texts displayed on the large digital screens at Piccadilly Circus in London (Figure 12) are examples of how typography helps shape the visual memory of the city square as a public space.

Figure 12: Screens in Piccadilly Circus **Source:** URL 5

2.1.1.4. The Role of Writing as An Informative Function in the Public Sphere

Signage in public spaces is one of the fundamental tools that enables individuals to communicate with their surroundings. Playing a significant role in visual communication, signage contributes not only to the presentation and organization of information but also to the construction of meaning in the environment. As the most fundamental communication tool assisting individuals in navigating their surroundings, text plays a crucial role in conveying necessary information to the target audience (Arthur & Passini, 1992, p. 13). From a graphic design perspective, the use of typographic hierarchy in the effective presentation of information makes the concept of text an effective tool in simplifying people's lives. Graphic design employs certain methods to systematically convey information through the text it uses, whether in environmental graphic design applications or in space-based graphic design applications.

It draws on the field of graphic design to shape an individual's perception of a sense of place, which is fundamental to the transmission of information and identity within the environment experienced in daily life. Graphic design fulfills its informative function through visual imagery, while also ensuring this function through the hierarchy established by typography. Becer (2019:185) explains this by pointing to the role of typography which he defines as a universal field in facilitating the exchange of information with a target audience for a specific purpose. As one of the fundamental elements of communication, the role of text in conveying information to the target audience in public spaces is evident in urban environments, transportation vehicles and systems, airports, and architectural structures.

Figure 13:Typography samples in British Library.
Source: Photographed by author

Figure 14:Greenwich Prime Meridian Typographic Samples. Source: URL 6

As a result, individuals interact with public spaces and are able to obtain the necessary information about the space they are in. Morin & Kelly (2018:728) define writing as a graphic code that conveys information with the characteristic of permanence. Figure 13 shows that information regarding the opening of the British Library building is displayed in writing at the library entrance, providing users with information about the history of the space. In another example, the Greenwich Observatory, located in London's Greenwich district, informs visitors about the prime meridian through lines and text created on the ground (Figure 14). The use of text not only makes information about the meridian and time measurement accessible to the target audience but also utilizes text as a communication tool in public spaces. In addition, digital graphic design systems are used in public spaces to speed up and facilitate users' access to information, and these systems include text-based informational graphics.

Figure 15:London City Wayfinding Signboard. Source: URL 7

In transportation systems, these platforms (Figure 15) which provide notifications about schedule changes, delays, and heavy traffic share real-time data with users. With the advancement of technology, these systems have become widespread in public spaces and serve as a medium through which graphic design fulfills the role of text in conveying complex data sets to the target audience in a clear and understandable manner. Digital information graphics that utilize text, typography, color, and interaction serve as design elements that establish an effective visual hierarchy tailored to public spaces.

3. CONCLUSION

A public space can be defined as a living space open to the shared use of individuals living in a community, where people can move about together and activities can take place. Public spaces provide individuals with a setting for social life and are designed to serve as spaces for communication and interaction. From the perspective of graphic design, it is evident that public space serves as a field of application for this discipline. Works such as wayfinding design for transportation systems, informational systems about a space, interactive and digital applications in city centers, posters for social campaigns, and spatial identity applications in museums demonstrate the presence of graphic design in public spaces.

The discipline of graphic design maintains its presence in the public sphere by utilizing tools inherent to the field, such as text, typography, and color. In the public sphere, text is one of the fundamental visual communication tools that regulates the interaction individuals establish with the space. It plays a significant role in shaping individuals' perception of space in the context of visual communication. When considered from a graphic design perspective, it can be seen to be related to fields such as environmental graphic design, informational design, and wayfinding design. This is because space and public space help individuals find meaning through the visual communication tools they interpret, thereby fostering a sense of belonging to that space. As a visual communication tool in public spaces, text also plays an effective role in maintaining public order.

In the relationship between public spaces and graphic design, typography serves as a means of communication that not only conveys information but also contributes to the identity of the space and the way users are guided. The use of typography in public spaces also contributes to individuals' processes of perceiving the space and developing a sense of belonging. Text used in cities also enables public life to be visible and legible in terms of the transmission of cultural memory. From this perspective, it is important that text used in public spaces be designed not only for aesthetic purposes but also with features that facilitate users' experiences and contribute to social communication.

REFERENCE

- Arthur, P., & Passini, R. (1992). *Wayfinding: People, signs and architecture*. McGraw-Hill Book Company.
- Aslanapa, O. (2018). *Türk sanatı*. Remzi Kitabevi.
- Atamaz, E. (2022). Mekansal iletişimde görsel iletişim tasarımının rolü ve önemi. Ö. Sayılğan, & A. İğit içinde, *Görsel iletişim tasarımı kuram ve araştırmaları* (s. 249-264). Nobel Akademik Yayıncılık.
- Barthes, R. (2022). *Görüntünün retoriği, sanat ve müzik*. Yapı Kredi Yayınları.
- Becer, E. (2019). *İletişim ve grafik tasarım*. Dost Yayınevi.
- Çelik, N., Bingöl, M., & Özkul, D. (2019). Kamusal alan bağlamında kentsel mekanlarda çağdaş sanat yansımaları. *Fine Arts*, 14(4), 284-297.
- Esgehzadeh Torbai, H. (2018). The role of environmental graphic in the identification of urban public spaces. *Civil Engineering Journal*, 1949-1954.
- Frutiger, A. (1998). *Signs and symbols: Their design and meaning*. Watson - Guptill.
- Güzer, C. A. (2024). *Sanat ve mimarlık*. Ayrıntı Basım Yayın.
- Habermas, J. (1962). *Strukturwandel der Öffentlichkeit, Untersuchungen zu einer kategorie der bürgerlichen gesellschaft*. Hermann Luchterhand Verlag.
- Habermas, J. (1993). *The structural transformation of the public sphere*. The MIT Press.
- Habermas, J. (2004). Kamusal alan. M. Özbek içinde, *Kamusal alan* (s. 95-102). Hil Yayın.
- Jean, G. (2023). *Yazı insanlığın belleği*. Yapı Kredi Yayınları.
- Lupton, E. (2010). *Thinking with type*. Princeton Architectural Press.
- Lynch, K. (2024). *Kent imgesi*. Türkiye İş Bankası Kültür Yayınları.
- Meggs, P., & Purvis, A. (2012). *Megg's history of graphic design*. John Wiley & Son, Inc.
- Morin, O., & Winters, J. (2018). Writing, graphic codes and asynchronous communication. *Cognitive science*, 727-743.
- Poulin, R. (2012). *Graphic design + architecture*. Rockport Publishing.
- Uçar, T. (2016). *Görsel iletişim ve grafik tasarım*. İnkılap Yayınevi .
- Yardımcı, S. (2014). *Kentsel değişim ve festivalizm küreselleşen istanbulda bienal*. İletişim Yayınları.

GÖRSEL KAYNAKÇA

URL 1: <https://www.serpentinegalleries.org/whats-on/serpentine-pavilion-2025-by-marina-tabassum/>

URL 2: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rosetta_Stone

URL 3: <https://banksyexplained.com/follow-your-dreams-cancelled-2010/>

URL 4: <https://banksyexplained.com/create-escape-march-2021/>

URL 5: <https://x.com/guidelondon/status/1989355440497443168>

URL 6: <https://londonpass.com/en/things-to-do/whats-the-big-deal-about-the-prime-meridian>

URL 7: <https://railuk.com/rail-news/rail-innovation-group-recognises-passageway-under-recognised-innovation-scheme/>